

ANALYSIS OF THE EXISTENCE OF MODERN BUILDINGS IN THE TONGKONAN KE'TE' KESU' AREA AS ONE OF THE PROPOSALS FOR UNESCO WORLD HERITAGE IN NORTH TORAJA REGENCY SOUTH SULAWESI PROVINCE

Mithen Lullulangi¹, Rahmansah² Raeny Tenriola Idrus³ Firnawati⁴ Yusaumi Ramadhanti Fitri Taufiq⁵

^{1,2,3,4,5} Lecturer of Civil Engineering Education and Planning, Faculty of Engineering, Universitas Negeri Makassar, Indonesia

ABSTRACT

This study analyzes the existence of modern buildings in Tongkonan Ke'te' Kesu', a traditional village proposed as a UNESCO World Heritage site. The research was conducted in North Toraja Regency, South Sulawesi Province, using a survey method to examine the impact of modernization on the Ke'te' Kesu' area. This study examines two main aspects: (1) the UNESCO criteria relevant to the Ke'te' Kesu' tourism area, and (2) the influence of modernization on the preservation of the traditional village. Data were collected through structured interviews, direct observation, and documentation. The data were analyzed using descriptive qualitative analysis as the basis for drawing conclusions. The results show that the Ke'te' Kesu' traditional village fulfills several UNESCO criteria required for inclusion on the permanent World Heritage List. These criteria include representing a masterpiece of human creative genius; demonstrating significant human values related to traditional architecture and monumental art; providing outstanding testimony to a living cultural tradition; serving as an exceptional example of a traditional settlement and land use that reflects human interaction with the environment, particularly in vulnerable conditions; and being directly associated with living traditions, beliefs, and works of art of outstanding universal value. However, the study also reveals that modernization has negatively affected the Ke'te' Kesu' traditional village. The presence of modern buildings constructed within the traditional village area may diminish its traditional and cultural value, potentially threatening its authenticity and sustainability as a cultural heritage site.

Keywords: *Tongkonan, Ke'te' Kesu', Modern Buildings, World Heritage.*

INTRODUCTION

Kompas.com (09/01/2023), wrote, We often hear that a place or an event is a cultural heritage. However, what is meant by cultural heritage? To understand it, here is the definition, types, and examples of cultural heritage! Definition of cultural heritage Reported from Heritage for Peace, cultural heritage is an expression of a way of life developed by a community and passed down from generation to generation. Cultural heritage is a legacy that represents a system of values, beliefs, traditions, lifestyles, and traces of a culture that are continuously passed down from the past to the present. How to Keep Cultural Heritage Sustainable? Reported from Humanities Libretxts, cultural heritage implies a common bond belonging to a community that represents the history and identity of the community in the past, present, and future. Cultural heritage consists of

two types, namely tangible cultural heritage and intangible cultural heritage. Tangible cultural heritage is a cultural heritage in the form of material or physical objects that can be seen and touched. Examples of material cultural heritage are temples, keris, batik, wayang, angklung, pinisi boats, noken (traditional Papuan bags), gamelan, paintings, drawings, prints, mosaics, books, historical sites, and also statues. Intangible cultural heritage is not limited to material objects only. But it also includes non-material (non-physical) elements that cannot be touched. For example, traditions, oral history, social practices, performing arts, traditional skills, and knowledge which contain cultural values and are passed on from generation to generation. Examples of intangible cultural heritage are traditional songs and music, language, traditional dances, traditional ceremonies, traditional celebrations, rituals, celebrations, weaving traditions, traditional games, skills, skills and traditional crafts.

Referring to the definition above, then comparing it with the cultural heritage in Ke'te' Kesu' can represent both elements of cultural heritage. The tangible cultural heritage is in the form of Tongkonan. For the implementation of traditional ceremonies in the Ke'te' Kesu' traditional village, all types of traditional ceremonies, both those included in Aluk Rambu Tuka' and Aluk Rambu Solo', have been carried out in this traditional village and are generally centered in Tongkonan, and supported by various ritual devices that are the fostered environment of Tongkonan such as: pangrampak, rante, simbuang, liang, paya/bala'kayan, lakkean, and others. Based on the explanation above, so that both elements of culture, both tangible culture and intangible culture, both exist in the Ke'te' Kesu' traditional village.

THEORETICAL REVIEW

Tongkonan

Lullulangi, et al (2007) explained that Tongkonan, comes from the word tongkon which means sitting in an abstract sense, the same as participating in or coming to attend a ritual ceremony or family ceremony. After getting the suffix "an" so that it becomes tongkonan which means more nuanced place. From the philosophical meaning, place shows function, and space = dimensional geographical area. Further developments tongkonan were given customary and governmental functions in the scope of regulating family order and a limited area that has harmonious substance relationships. The meaning is a place for deliberation, listening to orders, or a place to resolve customary problems that occur in society. Tongkonan is also the seat of the customary ruler or as the king's palace and the center of family ties. The word tongkonan actually has quite a lot of meanings, and is very dependent on the sentence and how to use it.

Furthermore, Sampebulu (2002) said, Tongkonan = Traditional house and customary built environment that has customary and governmental functions. This means that Tongkonan is not just a house but there is a built environment that accompanies it, and is united as a whole as a container for the unique Toraja cultural activities. Then talking about the built environment, Lullulangi, et al (2017) explains as follows:

The concept of *Tongkonan* as the center of traditional rulers and kinship ties usually consists of several houses each carrying out different custom functions, supported by: 1) rice barn, 2) *Rante* or the place of the *rambu soloq* (funeral ceremony), 3) grave (*Liang*), 4) bamboo and wooden gardens (*kombong*) for building materials if *Tongkonan* house is renovated, 5) rice fields and the fields (*uma* and *bela* ') as the livelihood of the residents of *Tongkonan's* house, and 6) *luba'ba* or *pangrampak* ie the space between *Tongkonan* and *Alang's* house. Thus, a *Tongkonan* group actually covers a broad

aspect as it covers aspects of traditional ceremonies, life arrangements, and other aspects of life so it can be concluded that *Tongkonan* is a Toraja traditional house building and its built environment.

Based on the narrative above, it explains that the Tongkonan environment consists of: Alang (Rice barn), Rante (Ceremonial place), Liang (Grave), Kombong, (Garden/cultivated forest) Uma (Rice field), and Luba'ba (Yard between Tongkonan House and Alang).

Cultural Heritage

According to Davidson (1991), cultural heritage is a product or result of physical culture from different traditions and spiritual achievements in the form of values from the past that are the main elements in the identity of a group or nation. Cultural heritage is the result of physical culture (tangible) and cultural values (intangible) from the past. Furthermore, Galla (2021) explains that physical cultural heritage (tangible heritage) is often classified into immovable cultural heritage (Immovable heritage), and movable cultural heritage (Movable heritage). Wardi (2008) said: Cultural heritage is a cultural wealth (Cultural capital) that has important value for understanding and developing history, science, and culture in order to foster community and national concerns.

UNESCO World Heritage Sites (UNESCO's World Heritage Sites) are special places (e.g. National Parks, Forests, Mountains, Lakes, Islands, Deserts, Buildings, Complexes, Regions, Villages, and Cities) that have been nominated for the international World Heritage program managed by the UNESCO World Heritage Committee, consisting of 21 groups (21 state parties) elected by the General Assembly in a 4-year contract. A World Heritage Site is a place of Culture and Nature, and objects that are meaningful to humanity and become a Heritage for future generations. Wikipedia (2022).

Quoting the Unesco Website, Lintang (2023) explains that Indonesia has six cultural heritages, and four natural heritages recognized by Unesco. The six cultural heritages are: 1) Borobudur Temple, 2) Prambanan Temple, 3) Sangiran Early Man Site, 4) Bali Subak System, 5) Ombilin Coal Mine Sawahlunto, and 6) Sumbu Filosofi Yogyakarta. Then the four natural heritages recognized by UNESCO are: 1) Komodo National Park, 2) Ujung Kulon National Park, 3) Lorentz National Park, and 4) Sumatra Tropical Forest Heritage.

Then, those included in the tentative list of world heritage by UNESCO in 2009, there are six cultural heritages, namely: 1) Toraja Traditional Settlement, 2) Bawomataluo Site, 3) Muara Takus Compound Site, 4) Muarajambi Temple Compounds, 5) Trowulan, Former Capital City of Majapahit Kingdom, and 6) Prehistoric Cave Sites in Maros Pangkep. Then in 2015, there were three additional cultural heritages, namely: 1) Traditional Settlement at Nagari Sijunjung, West Sumatra, 2) Semarang Old Town, Central Java, and 3) Sangkulirang-Mangkalihat Karts: Prehistoric Rock Art Area, West Kalimantan.

Based on the explanation above, the Ke'te' Kesu' traditional village which will be the object of this research, its status is still on the temporary list (Tentative List), so in order to try to be included in the permanent list, through the Ministry of Agrarian Affairs and Spatial Planning of the Republic of Indonesia, it is trying to complete the data to meet the criteria set by Unesco, where the data must be supported by scientific studies or research results.

Selection Criteria

Muller (2010), explains that the prerequisites for nomination as a UNESCO World Heritage site are the fulfillment of certain criteria. In addition to "authenticity", namely historical

authenticity, the criterion of "integrity" must also be met: the potential of the World Heritage site must be preserved intact.

In addition, the uniqueness of the site must be documented, "outstanding universal value". Outstanding testimony to traditions and cultural heritage or to civilizations that are still alive or have disappeared. Evidence of these criteria must be presented at the stage of the national Tentative List nomination.

Then the criteria explained by the Operational Guidelines for the Implementation of the World Heritage Convention (UNESCO World Heritage Center 1992-2024), explain as follows: To be included in the World Heritage List, a site must have outstanding universal value and meet at least one of the ten selection criteria. These criteria are explained in the Operational Guidelines for the Implementation of the World Heritage Convention which, in addition to the text of the Convention, is also the main working tool regarding World Heritage. These criteria are periodically revised by the Committee to reflect the evolution of the World Heritage concept itself. Until the end of 2004, World Heritage sites were selected based on six cultural criteria and four natural criteria. With the adoption of the revised Operational Guidelines for the Implementation of the World Heritage Convention, there are only ten criteria. These are as follows: 1) To represent a masterpiece of human creative genius; 2) To demonstrate an important exchange of human values, in a particular period or in a world cultural area, concerning developments in architecture or technology, monumental art, town planning or landscape design; 3) To bear unique or at least outstanding testimony to a living or disappeared cultural tradition or civilization; 4) To be an outstanding example of a type of building, architectural or technological ensemble, or landscape illustrating an important stage in human history; 5) To be an outstanding example of traditional settlements, land use or sea use representative of a culture (or cultures), or of human interaction with the environment, especially when the environment is vulnerable to the effects of irreversible changes; 6) To be associated directly or tangibly with living events or traditions, with ideas or beliefs, with works of art or literature of outstanding universal significance. (The Committee considers that this criterion should be used in conjunction with the other criteria); 7) Contain superlative natural phenomena or areas of outstanding natural beauty and aesthetic value; 8) Be outstanding examples representing significant stages in the history of the earth, including the record of life, significant ongoing geological processes in the development of landscapes, or significant geomorphic or physiographic features; 9) Be outstanding examples representing significant ongoing ecological and biological processes in the evolution and development of terrestrial, freshwater, coastal and marine ecosystems and plant and animal communities; and 10) Contain the most important and significant natural habitats for the conservation of biological diversity, including habitats of threatened species of outstanding universal value from a scientific or conservation standpoint.

These are the 10 criteria set by Unesco to be used as a reference in order to record a world heritage, both cultural and natural heritage. And these criteria will also be used as parameters in assessing the Ke'te' Kesu' traditional village, although substantially it has been included in Unesco's temporary records as one of the world's cultural heritages, but it is expected that what will be studied in this study will also strengthen the existing criteria, including the study of the influence of modern technology on this object, which may be used as a reference for strengthening so that this object can be recorded as one of the world's cultural heritages that is permanent, to follow the 10 objects that were previously determined as world cultural heritage objects.

RESEARCH METHOD

This research is an ex post facto research, namely research conducted to examine an event that has occurred and then trace back to find out the factors that can cause the incident. In addition, this research is a qualitative research because it will use qualitative descriptive in processing and analyzing data before drawing conclusions. The research was conducted in the Ke'te' Kesu' Traditional Village, Mamasa Regency, South Sulawesi Province. The research variables to be studied are: 1) Selection criteria by Unesco 2) The influence of modernization on the object of research. Data collection techniques are direct observation in the field, in-depth interviews with community leaders, especially the grandchildren of the heirs of the Ke'te' Kesu' traditional village and literature studies on the writings of researchers related to this research. Data were analyzed descriptively qualitatively, with the following steps: Data collection, data display/presentation, data reduction, and drawing conclusions.

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Research Results

General Description of Ke'te' Kesu' Traditional Village

Lullulangi, et al (2007) explained that: The Ke'te' Kesu' traditional village is located in Bonoran Village, Lembang Ba'tan, Kesu' District, North Toraja Regency, approximately 4 km from Rantepao City. In this village, there are five traditional houses and approximately twelve rice barns that reflect the unique Toraja traditional village. The oldest Tongkonan is Tongkonan Kesu' which is approximately ten centuries old, and has undergone several renovations. This Tongkonan was previously located on the peak of a rocky mountain called Kaesungan/Kesu' approximately one kilometer from Ke'te' now. It was first built as Tongkonan Pesio' Aluk by the first traditional ruler, who was titled Puang Ri Kesu' around 900 AD, so this Tongkonan is the oldest Tongkonan among other famous Tongkonan in Tana Toraja.

During the reign of Siambe' Pong Panimba as the Head of Kesu' District during the Dutch colonial era, Tongkonan Kesu' was moved from the mountain to the Ke'te' location as his residence and also as the center of Kesu' traditional government. Although previously at that location there had been a Tongkonan, namely Tongkonan Bamba as the Tongkonan of the Customary Chief or Sokkong Bayu from Bonoran village which was built around 1680 by the traditional leader Siambe' Sa'bu Lompo.

So the traditional village of Ke'te' Kesu' which has its current form, is only around 344 years old, even though the oldest Tongkonan in Tana Toraja, namely Tongkonan Kesu', is located at that location and has been designated as one of the cultural heritages with registration number 290 which needs to be preserved and protected.

Customary Functions

All Tongkonan in Ke'te' Kesu' have different customary roles. And based on the results of an interview with Sarungngallo (2001), the customary functions of each Tongkonan are as follows: 1) Tongkonan Kesu'. It is a Pesio' Aluk Tongkonan, and the main house with seven front pillars, with the position of Tongkonan Layuk or Pesio' Aluk (as the elder/deliberation council). 2) Tongkonan Bamba. Tongkonan Bamba was built around 1680 with the position of Sokkong Bayu or customary leader of the Bonoran village, by the customary leader Siambe' Sa'bu Lompo

(Government executor). 3) Tongkonan Lelating. This Tongkonan is a combination of three Tongkonan, each: (a) Tongkonan To' Kaluku who serves as an advisor, (b) Tongkonan To' Sendana who serves as Kaparengngesan in the economic field, and (c) Tongkonan Lelating who serves as Kaparengngesan as a member of the Tongkonan Bamba government. 4) Tongkonan Tonga. Is the Tongkonan Kaparengngesan as a member of the traditional government of Tongkonan Bamba (the driver of energy/community), and 5) Tongkonan Borong. As Tongkonan Pa'rapuan (Batu A'riri). Although it does not have a traditional function or kaparengngesan, it is still a close relative of the owner of another tongkonan so that it is located in the Ke'te' Kesu' traditional village location. Apart from the five traditional houses above, in this location there is also a traditional house that is larger than the other traditional houses, which is a new building and functions as a museum. To see the layout of each Tongkonan, you can see the site plan in the image below.

Description:

- T1 = Tongkonan Borong
- T2 = Tongkonan Tonga
- T3 = Tongkonan Kesu'
- T4 = Tongkonan Lelating
- T5 = Tongkonan Bamba

L1 to L14 = Rice Barn (alang)

A1 to A6 = Modern House (owner's residence)

Figure 1. Site Plan of the Original Village of Ke'te' Kesu'
Before many modern buildings were built around it
Source: Lullulangi, et al (2007).

Figure 2. Aerial Photo of Ke'te' Kesu' Traditional Village
Source: Wahyudi (2020).

In Figure 2. above, a Tongkonan-shaped building is visible and its proportions are larger in the second position from the right of the image, which is the Sasana Budaya building which is a new building, and also functions as a museum where various heirlooms related to the Ke'te' Kesu' Traditional Village are stored. (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Photo of the Sasana Budaya Building of the Ke'te' Kesu' Traditional Village
Source: Research Results

In terms of model, this building is exactly the same as the existing Tongkonan, both in terms of shape, proportion, ornaments and so on. However, the undercarriage of the house (Suluk banua) which is walled with modern materials (zinc plates) also has an effect on reducing the traditional value of this traditional village, which can actually use local structural materials made

of strong wood, which are still the same as the original structural materials of the Tongkonan, so that the philosophy of Tongkonan construction which should not use nails or other materials made of metal is still fulfilled.

New/Modern Buildings in the Ke'te' Kesu' Traditional House Complex

The Ke'te' Kesu' traditional village is a very unique traditional village and is the oldest traditional village in North Toraja Regency. Although this village was actually built in 1680 (Lullulangi, et al, 2007) or is currently 344 years old, one of the Tongkonans in this traditional house complex, namely Tongkonan Kesu' as Tongkonan Pesio' Aluk which was moved from the mountain, was built by Puang Ri Kesu' around 900 AD or is currently 1,124 years old, so this traditional village is very worthy of being listed as one of the world's cultural heritage sites. In the development of the increasingly modern era, one of the things that is very unfortunate is that the stakeholders of this cultural heritage site do not understand how to maintain the originality of the cultural site, in this case both the Ke'te' Kesu' Foundation as the manager and the local government. This is evident from the discovery of several modern buildings in the traditional village complex. From the researcher's investigation, several modern buildings were found that actually reduce the traditional value of this traditional village, which can be described as follows:

1. Souvenir shops that highlight modern buildings

The souvenir shops that the researcher means are several souvenir shops that highlight modern buildings starting from the gate of the site to the inside of the traditional house complex, even to the Tongkonan built environment, namely the liang (grave) located in the western position or the back of the Tongkonan. There are several images that the researcher can display as follows:

Figure 4 Souvenir Shop at the gate of Ke'te' Kesu' Traditional Village
Source: Research Results

Figure 5. Souvenir Shop inside the Ke'te' Kesu' Traditional House complex
Source: Research Results

Figure 6. Souvenir Shop in the western part of the Ke'te' Kesu' Traditional House complex
Source: Research Results

The picture of the souvenir shop above is just a sample of the many souvenir shops that exist with a modern building feel that indirectly reduces the traditional value of an original cultural site. Its existence is actually very beneficial from an economic perspective because it is a place for

visitors to shop, which can provide income for the management family and the existence of this souvenir shop is not wrong in fact it supports Sapta Pesona in the field of Tourism, namely the existence of souvenirs that can be taken home by tourists. However, what the researcher highlights in this case is the architectural appearance of the souvenir shop building. Although the appearance of the souvenir shop still adopts the traditional Toraja architectural decoration in the form of traditional Toraja carvings, the shape of the building is modern, which should also be in the form of a Tongkonan house, although in a smaller proportion.

2. Modern housing in the form of a house from relatives or family

The existence of a house building as a residence for the management family is a modern building that greatly reduces the traditional value of the traditional village, which is actually a permanent building that has been permitted to build from the North Toraja Regency Government. With the issuance of the building permit, as an indication that the Regional Government also does not understand the essence of traditional values that need to be maintained as an important point so that this cultural heritage can be determined not only as a temporary list, but can be upgraded to a permanent list of world heritage cultural heritage (World Heritage).

As a sample, the following are several photos of modern buildings in the traditional house complex as follows:

Figure 7. Modern buildings in the Ke'te' Kesu' traditional house complex
Source: Research Results

Figure 8. A new modern house with a building permit (IMB) in the Ke'te' Kesu' traditional house complex.
Source: Research Results

3. Prayer room in the cultural site complex

A prayer room (mushollah) is an important supporting element of a tourist attraction, particularly for Muslim tourists. It can be used by tourists during their visit and during prayer times. However, to maintain the traditional and original values of the original cultural site and prevent it from being influenced by other cultures, whether modernization or religious elements, the placement of these supporting facilities should be considered so that they do not appear to be integrated with the protected cultural site. Therefore, it is best to place the prayer room (mushollah) not within the traditional house complex, but rather near the entrance or another accessible location without disrupting the architectural unity of the protected cultural site.

The actual condition at the Ke'te' Kesu' traditional house site, where the prayer room was built, is actually located within a row of rice barns, which are still part of the traditional house complex, as shown in the image below.

Figure 9. Prayer room in the Ke'te' Kesu' traditional house complex
Source: Research Results

Looking at the position of the prayer room in Figure 4.8 above, the rows of rice barns visible on the left and right edges of the photo indicate that the prayer room is very close to and integrated with a protected cultural site.

Analysis of the Ke'te' Kesu' Traditional House Complex Based on UNESCO Criteria

Unesco uses ten criteria as parameters or indicators for assessing a cultural site, as established through the revised World Heritage Convention. The researcher will use these ten criteria as the basis for assessing the current condition of the Ke'te' Kesu' Traditional House Complex as the basis for qualitative analysis in this study. Although the researcher believes that relevant parties and possibly other researchers have already done so, Ke'te' Kesu' has been included on the tentative list as a cultural heritage site with registration number 290, which requires preservation and protection.

In the explanation above, which is quoted from the Operational Guidelines for the Implementation of the World Heritage Convention (UNESCO World Heritage Centre 1992-2024), to be included in the World Heritage List, a site must have outstanding universal value and meet at least one of the ten selection criteria, as follows:

1. To represent a masterpiece of human creative genius.

The Tongkonan and its built environment are a testament to the genius of the Torajan ancestors. This unique traditional house, situated opposite a rice barn, adheres to the traditional philosophy of Simuane-Tallang. This means that everything in the universe exists in pairs. There is night, there is day; there is male, there is female, and so on. The traditional house, as the center of the Tongkonan, is paired with a rice barn, built facing each other. This unique traditional architectural concept, and the space between these two buildings, called Pangrampak or Tarampak, plays a crucial role as the center of Torajan cultural activities, including the Rambu Tukaq (thanksgiving ceremony) and the Rambu Soloq (mourning ceremony).

Furthermore, the Tongkonan concept is also supported by other built environments, namely Rante as the center of Rambu Soloq activities, a special place for slaughtering sacrificial animals, equipped with a simbuang stone, a stone planted on a stand to tie the buffalo to be slaughtered; Lakkian, a place to lay the corpse during the ceremony; and Bala'kayan, a place where the sacrificial meat is distributed to all attendees, especially to the traditional leaders associated with the Tongkonan. Furthermore, it is supported by Uma (rice fields) as a source of life, and kombong, a maintained forest that serves an ecological function.

Observing the uniqueness of the Ke'te' Kesu' traditional village, consisting of the Tongkonan and its built environment, the researcher concludes that the first UNESCO criterion above is met.

2. To demonstrate the exchange of significant humanitarian values, over a specific time period or within a global cultural region, regarding developments in architecture or technology, monumental art, urban planning, or landscape design.

The second criterion, when viewed from the perspective of humanitarian values over time, is that this traditional village will be 344 years old as of 2024, and one of the oldest Tongkonans within the site complex is 1,124 years old. This means that this cultural site is quite ancient, and the human activities utilizing this architectural product have proven to fulfill humanitarian values.

Furthermore, in terms of architectural development, as a traditional architectural product, it must maintain its authenticity, thus avoiding the influence of modernization, such as the use of modern structural materials. Its ability to maintain its authenticity over centuries makes this cultural site a monumental architectural art. Furthermore, in terms of landscape design, Kombong's existence as a cultivated forest and landscape serves as historical evidence that the ancestors of the Toraja people were able to create environmentally friendly architectural products. With this explanation, the researcher concludes that the second criterion is also met.

3. To provide unique, or at least extraordinary, testimony to living or lost cultural traditions or civilizations.

Regarding unique cultural testimony and living cultural traditions, Tongkonan Ke'te' Kesu' can testify to a unique culture and living cultural traditions from ancient times to the present. This is evidenced by the existence of the traditional village, which has survived for 344 years, and one Tongkonan, which is 1,124 years old. Thus, this third criterion is met.

4. It is an outstanding example of a building type, architectural or technological ensemble, or landscape that illustrates a significant stage in human history.

Of the several key terms in this fourth criterion, the traditional architecture applied to the Tongkonan in Ke'te' Kesu' can serve as an example, namely the ability of the Tongkonan's heirs to maintain and preserve it, thus depicting historical stages from the past to the present.

5. It is an outstanding example of a traditional settlement, land use, or sea use that represents a culture (or cultures), or human interaction with the environment, especially when the environment is vulnerable to the impacts of irreversible change.

Regarding this sixth criterion, there is no doubt that the Ke'te' Kesu' cultural site is an outstanding example of a traditional settlement, representing the unique Torajan culture, while maintaining natural sustainability, as demonstrated by one of the Tongkonan's built environments, the Kombong, or built-up forest, located on the western side of the Ke'te' Kesu' Tongkonan Complex. This Kombong forest, composed of selected bamboo and wood, also serves an ecological function. Therefore, this fifth criterion is met.

6. It must be directly or tangibly linked to living events or traditions, ideas, beliefs, and works of art and literature of exceptional universal significance.

The Ke'te' Kesu' Tongkonan area represents living events or traditions, namely the traditions and culture of the Torajan people that have been well-preserved from ancient times to the present day. Both the rambu tukaq and rambu soloq traditions remain preserved and are carried out at the Ke'te' Kesu' Tongkonan as a forum for community activities supporting these cultures. Thus, this sixth criterion is met.

7. Containing superlative natural phenomena or areas of exceptional natural beauty and aesthetic value.

The Tongkonan Ke'te' Kesu' site plan is designed in such a way that both the core of the Tongkonan and its built environment, particularly the expanse of uma (rice fields) in front of the Tongkonan, are complemented by the lush trees of the cultivated forest behind the Tongkonan, making this cultural site remarkably beautiful and at one with nature. However, over time, this beautiful aesthetic has been disrupted by the presence of modern buildings built around the traditional houses.

8. Serves as an outstanding example representing important stages in Earth's history, including records of life, important geological processes ongoing in the development of the landscape, or significant geomorphic or physiographic features.

Regarding geological processes, the Tongkonan Ke'te' Kesu' area, particularly the built environment of Liang (cemetery), is characterized by a limestone mountain on the west side of the Tongkonan, which serves as a burial complex. The limestone mountains indicate ancient geological processes, proving that this area, and/or the Toraja region in general, known as Tondok Lepongan Bulan Tana Matarik Allo, was once part of the sea, which later became land after geological processes thousands of years ago.

9. Serve as an outstanding example representing important ongoing ecological and biological processes in the evolution and development of terrestrial, freshwater, coastal, and marine ecosystems, as well as plant and animal communities.

Regarding this ninth criterion, none of the keywords in the Tongkonan Ke'te' Kesu' area appear to be able to be analyzed or narrated.

10. Contain the most important and significant natural habitat for biodiversity conservation, including habitats of threatened species of outstanding universal value from a scientific or conservation perspective.

Similar to criterion nine above, none of the keywords in criterion 10, the Tongkonan Ke'te' Kesu' site, however, can be analyzed or narrated. Based on a qualitative analysis of the traditional village site or Tongkonan Ke'te' Kesu', based on the 10 (ten) criteria used as parameters or indicators by UNESCO to assess a cultural site, which are determined through the revised World Heritage Convention, of the 10 criteria there are 5 criteria that are very well met, there are 3 (three) criteria that are close to being met, and 2 (two) criteria that cannot be commented on.

2. Discussion

Based on the research results, the Tongkonan Ke'te' Kesu' cultural site, which has been included on the tentative list as a cultural heritage site with registration number 290 that requires preservation and protection, has generally met five main criteria and three criteria that are close to being met. This contrasts with Muller's (2010) opinion that a prerequisite for nomination as a UNESCO World Heritage site is the fulfillment of certain criteria. In addition to "authenticity," namely historical authenticity, the "integrity" criterion must also be met: the potential of a World Heritage site must be preserved intact. Therefore, Muller's explanation is almost entirely fulfilled

at the Tongkonan Ke'te' Kesu' cultural site, making it appropriate for inclusion on the permanent list of world heritage sites requiring protection.

Furthermore, the Organizational Guidelines for the Implementation of the World Heritage Convention (UNESCO World Heritage Centre 1992-2024) explain that to be included on the World Heritage List, a site must have outstanding universal value and meet at least one of the ten selection criteria. This means that if the site being assessed meets one of the ten criteria established by UNESCO, it can be included as a UNESCO protected site. This explanation, combined with the research findings, shows that the Tongkonan Ke'te' Kesu' site convincingly meets five of the ten criteria, with three nearly meeting them. Therefore, based on this analysis, the Tongkonan Ke'te' Kesu' traditional village site is highly deserving of being upgraded from the provisional list to the permanent list as one of Indonesia's cultural heritage sites, alongside Borobudur Temple, Prambanan Temple, the Sangiran Early Man Site, the Balinese Subak System, the Umbilin Coal Mine, and the Yogyakarta Philosophical Axis (Lintang, 2023).

The only potential obstacle is the presence of several modern buildings within the Ke'te' Kesu' traditional village area, as described in the research findings above. Therefore, the researcher hopes that all stakeholders involved in the Tongkonan Ke'te' Kesu' cultural site will recognize this weakness and strive to improve it so that it does not become an obstacle when the UNESCO Verification Team evaluates this cultural site for inclusion on the permanent list of World Heritage sites. Hopefully.

CONCLUSION

The research results show that: 1) The criteria that the Ke'te' Kesu' traditional village meets as a requirement for inclusion on the UNESCO permanent list of protected areas are: (a) To represent a masterpiece of human creative genius, (b) To demonstrate an important exchange of human values, within a specific time period or within a world cultural area, regarding developments in architecture or technology, monumental art, urban planning or landscape design, (c) To provide unique or at least exceptional testimony to a living or lost cultural tradition or civilization, (d) To be an outstanding example of traditional settlement, land use, or sea use representing a culture (or cultures), or human interaction with the environment, especially when the environment is vulnerable to the impacts of irreversible change, (e) To be directly or tangibly associated with living events or traditions, with ideas, or with beliefs, with works of art and literature of outstanding universal significance. 2). The impact of modernization on the Ke'te' Kesu' traditional village, namely the presence of modern buildings within the Ke'te' Kesu' traditional village site, can diminish its traditional value.

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